

ENHANCED LOAD TRANSFER IN CARBON NANOTUBES- REINFORCED ALUMINUM

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ABSTRACT

Although carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are reinforced into aluminum alloys to enhance mechanical properties by liquid process, the underlying strengthening mechanism has not been clarified yet. Here we report a load transfer mechanism to explain the enhanced mechanical properties in CNT-reinforced pure aluminum. The mechanically pulverized Al in paraffin oil and the CNTs dispersed in dichloroethane (DCE) solution were mixed together for further sonication. After drying and removing oil, the mixed powder was sintered and the solid-type sample was finally obtained by the melt-blending process. Formation of covalent bonds between Al and CNT walls was confirmed by the existence of Al_4C_3 in XRD, resulting in load transfer for strengthening mechanical properties. The extruded sample revealed improved yield strength and tensile strength by 60 % and 23 %, respectively, at an addition of 0.2 wt% CNTs. These enhancements are well corroborated with the predicted values from shear lag model that explains the load transfer mechanism.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aluminum is a light metal with high corrosion resistance, high ductility, and low melting point compared to its counterpart iron metal, which is used in various industry areas. However, poor mechanical performance limits its further use. Thus, improvement of the mechanical strength of Al using composite approach has been the main stream of researches, such as Al-ceramic, Al-fiber, Al-nano materials composites. Above all, because carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been known to possess superb mechanical properties with extremely high aspect ratio [1], Al-CNT composites were actively studied. Strengthening Al with CNTs in general relies on the aspect ratio, degree of alignment of the CNTs, and furthermore the interfacial strength between Al matrix and CNT surface. Thus, major issues in Al-CNT composite are strong bonding between CNTs and Al matrix, and alignment of CNT to load direction without damage of CNTs.

Another issue is the fabrication method. Powder metallurgy [2-4] and thermal spray method [5] have been widely used for fabrication of Al-CNT composite. Yet, these methods are not appropriate for industrial-scale production. Liquid process has been proposed in order to apply for the mass production. Several approaches using liquid process have been tested: stir-casting, die-casting, and squeeze casting with pretreatment of CNTs such as Ni-plating [6], SiC-coating [7]. Although such attempts improved mechanical properties of hardness or strength to some degree, the underlying strengthening mechanism has been far from being clearly understood. The studies have been focused on the Al alloy matrix of A356 [6-9] or Al239D [10]. However, the strengthening mechanism of alloys is very complex because of precipitation of metallic compounds, effect of heat treatment, and complicated microstructures.

In this study, we fabricated the pure Al matrix CNT composite to verify strengthening mechanism. In addition, we propose a specific casting method for the uniform dispersion of CNTs in Al matrix,

preventing the oxidation of CNTs and Al matrix and forming the Al-C covalent bonds between Al and CNT interface. These conditions lead to effective load transfer from the Al to the CNTs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Synthesis of Al-CNT composite

The preparation of Al-CNT composite samples consists of seven steps: 1) wet ball milling of Al, 2) dispersion of CNTs in dichloroethane (DCE), 3) mixing the Al with dispersed CNTs solution, 4) removal of oil by heat treatment, 5) sintering, 6) melt-blending, and 7) extrusion. The Al powder (Samjeon Chemicals, Korea) was gas-atomized. Paraffin oil was added during ball-milling to prevent oxidation of Al particles. The ball milling process was performed by a planetary ball-miller (Pulverisette 6, Fristch, Germany). The 5 mm zirconia balls were used as the milling media in a 500 ml carbon steel container. The mass ratio of Al powder : Oil : ZrO₂ balls was fixed to 2 : 1 : 4 under Ar gas. The ball milling time was maintained for 4 hours at a fixed 300 rpm. In order to uniformly disperse the CNTs (multiwalled CNTs, Hanwha Nanotech Corporation, Korea) in solution, the CNTs were dipped into the DCE solution and dispersed using homogenizer (ULH-700S, Sonosmasher) for 90 min. The oil-coated and ball milled Al powder was mixed with DCE-CNT solution by homogenizer for 30 min again. The CNTs : Al mass ratio was fixed to 1 : 99. DCE solution was removed by drying in vacuum at 80 °C. The dried mixture was inserted into the steel mold and heated up to 500 °C for 30 min in Ar atmosphere to remove oil, which was further heated up at 580 °C for 20 min. The mixture was then sintered into a coin form of 20 mm diameter by pressurizing at 500 MPa under Ar ambient. Melt-blending process was performed in high-frequency induction furnace (Eltek, Korea) at 680 °C in vacuum ($\sim 10^{-3}$ torr). When the pure Al was completely melted, the weighed Al-CNT composite was inserted into molten pure Al. The blending was performed using a graphite impeller at 500 rpm for 20 min, and then the molten Al-CNT composite was casted into a carbon mold (25 mm in diameter). The nominal concentration of the CNTs was 0.2 wt%. The casted composite was extruded from 25 to 8 mm in diameter at 550 °C. The raw Al sample as a reference was also fabricated by the same process.

2.2 Characterization

The morphology of Al powder and composite was characterized by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JEOL 6700F). The dispersion of CNTs in DCE solution was characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS, DLS-8000, Otsuka electronics). The remaining oil was also measured by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR, IFS-66s, Bruker). The structural changes in the Al-CNT composite were further characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD, Rotaflex D/MAX system, Rigaku) using Cu K α radiation with a wavelength of 1.54 Å. Mechanical properties were measured using an ultimate tensile tester (DTU-900MH, Deakyung) and the tensile test specimens were re-formed with a diameter of 4.0 ± 0.1 mm and a gage length of 20.0 ± 0.1 mm, based on ASTM E8/E8M. The tension test was performed with an extension speed of 2 mm/min.

3 RESULTS

The cold welding phenomenon of metal powder occurs in the ball milling process because ductile metal particles are aggregated during ball milling. Another serious problem of ball milling process is oxidation of metal surface which often leads to degrade the mechanical properties and will prevent the formation of effective bonds between Al and CNTs. In this study, the ball milling was proceeded in an oxygen-free solution (paraffin oil, CH₃(CH₂)_nCH₃). The aluminum particles were covered with oil during wet ball milling. The oil plays a role as a process control agent and prevents Al particles from being oxidized. Figure 1a shows morphology of initial Al powders. During wet-ball milling, the Al powders experienced the fracture and micro-rolling, while the paraffin oil prevented welding between Al particles. As a result, the Al particles were deformed into a disk shape of approximately 20 ~ 100 μ m in diameter and ~ 5 μ m in thickness, as can be seen in Fig. 1b. In the wet ball milling method, oxidation of the fractured surfaces was prevented by the coated paraffin oil immediately after fracture. This oxide-free Al surface will easily form covalent bonds with CNTs. As a consequence, the quantity of total aluminum oxide did not increase.

Figure 1: SEM micrograph of (a) initial Al powders, (b) pulverized Al powders, (c) surface of Al-CNT mixture.

The CNTs tend to form the cluster due to their strong van der Waals interaction between long CNTs. The CNT powder was dispersed in DCE solution using homogenizer. Use of DCE was necessary due to its nature of oxygen-free species ($\text{ClCH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{Cl}$). The dispersed CNT solution was mixed with oil-coated Al particles for uniform dispersion of CNTs on the surface of Al particles. While the mixture was treated by homogenizer, the paraffin oil was dissolved in DCE solution. As a result, Al particles and CNTs are homogeneously dispersed in solution. The DCE solution was removed through vacuum dry but the paraffin oil was still retained. Individual CNTs were dispersed uniformly on the surface of the milled Al particles. This was identified in Fig. 1c. Figure 2a is DLS result of CNTs dispersed DCE solution, before mixing process. The CNTs were uniform dispersed in DCE solution without aggregation.

The generated gas from remained paraffin oil during high temperature processes created micro pores, leading to generate the crack. Thus, the remaining paraffin oil was removed at temperature annealing of $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ before sintering. Figure 2b shows the FT-IR results of each step. The black curve shows the FT-IR spectrum of initial paraffin oil, the blue curve from oil-coated Al particles, and the red curve from de-oiled Al particles (heat treatment at $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The powder samples such as oil-coated Al powder, and de-oiled Al powder were pretreated with KBr powder for effective measurement of FT-IR. Special care is required for analysis due to hygroscopic nature of KBr. The peaks of 2920 and 2853 cm^{-1} correspond to C-H stretching modes, while the peaks of 1463 and 1375 cm^{-1} correspond to the C-H bending modes [11]. These peaks are representative of paraffin oil's ($\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{CH}_3$) IR spectrum. Every powder samples have 3425 and 1623 cm^{-1} broad peaks which are related with O-H bonds from H_2O attached in KBr. In the result of oil-coated Al (blue curve), the presence of 2920 , 2853 and 1463 , 1375 cm^{-1} peaks are evidence of existing paraffin oil in Al powder. After heat treatment (red curve), we cannot observe such C-H related peaks.

The oil-coated Al-CNT mixture was inserted in the metal mold and heated up to $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for de-oiling under Ar atmosphere. The heat treatment was kept until complete evaporation of paraffin oil, followed by sintering process. The sintering process was operated at $580\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As a result, Al_4C_3 covalent bonds were generated through reaction between Al and CNTs. Figure 2c shows the XRD results. The Al_4C_3 peaks were marked as inverted triangles in addition to Al peaks marked as squares. The simply sintered Al-CNT sample showed some degree of the formation of Al_4C_3 , although the melt-blended Al-CNT clearly revealed carbide formation. In melting blending process, high-frequency induction furnace (HFIF) equipment provided the vortex in molten Al with mechanical stirring by an impeller. This leads to improve the uniform dispersion of CNTs in the molten Al. The oxidation of Al was prevented because of vacuum process so as to alleviate the effect of reducing fluidity in casting process. Increasing the crystallinity of Al_4C_3 was observed when the operating temperature of the melt blending process was $680\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is higher than that of the sintering process. Increasing Al_4C_3 reaction improves wettability between Al matrix and carbon materials [12]. The formation of Al_4C_3 is helpful in stress transfer to CNTs and is necessary for implementing effective load transfer [3, 13].

Figure 2: (a) Dynamic light scattering analysis result of CNT dispersed DCE solution, (b) FT-IR result of initial paraffin oil, oil coated Al powder, de-oiled Al powder and (c) XRD result of Al-CNT composites at different processes

The Casted Al-CNT composite was extruded finally to improve the mechanical properties. The CNTs are expected to align along the extrusion direction, improving the mechanical properties [3, 13]. Figure 3a shows the typical tensile test curves from extruded pure Al and Al-CNT composite. By adding 0.2 wt% CNTs, the mechanical properties were improved. Table 1 summarizes the values from Fig. 3a. With only 0.2 wt% CNTs, 60% in the yield strength and 23% in the tensile strength were improved. The underlying mechanism will be described in the discussion section.

Figure 3b shows the fracture surface of the extruded Al-CNT composite after the test of mechanical strength. The CNTs were good wetted with Al matrix due to strong bonds with Al. In order to confirm the existence of CNTs in Al matrix, the Al-CNT composite sample was etched in acid solution (HNO₃ + HCl) to melt away Al and filtered to obtain only CNTs. Figure 3c demonstrates that the remaining CNTs maintains their initial structure and no significant structural damage is observed from SEM characterization. From these results, we conclude that our fabrication method provides no appreciable damage. Unlike the significant improvement of the mechanical strength, elongation was reduced from 17% to 9.5%. This is quite typical from the normal metal matrix with nano materials. In general, most of the studies observed the reduction in the elongation in metal-CNTs composites [3, 4, 13]. However, its elongation, synthesized by our method, is still within the acceptable range of application in industry.

4 DISCUSSION

Three strengthening mechanisms have been proposed in Al-CNT composites: Load transfer, generation of dislocation by thermal mismatch, and Orowan looping system. They in general occur simultaneously [13, 14]. The strengthening of composite in a fiber shape of reinforcement (CNT), can be analyzed based on shear lag model. The shear lag model had been suggested by Kelly and Tyson for fiber composite. The applied stress is transferred to the fibers through an interfacial shear stress [15]. For analysis by shear lag model, a perfect interface bonding between matrix (Al) and reinforcement (CNTs) is presumed. This is justified in our case by the formation of Al₄C₃ at interface. We compare the experimental value and predicted value by this theory. The yield strength can be calculated by Eqn. (1) [16],

$$\sigma_{Y.C} = \sigma_{Y.M} \left[V_R \left(\frac{S_{eff} + 2}{2} \right) + V_M \right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: (a) Tensile test curves from raw Al and Al-CNT composite, SEM micrographs of (b) fracture surface of the Al-CNT composite after tensile test and (c) remained CNTs after etching.

The $\sigma_{Y,C}$, $\sigma_{Y,M}$ are the yield strength of composite and matrix, respectively. The V_R and V_M are volume fraction of reinforcement (CNTs) and matrix (Al), respectively. The S_{eff} is an effective aspect ratio. Since the alignment of reinforcement in matrix affects the strengthening, we consider this parameter. The S_{eff} is defined as follows in Eqn. (2):

$$S_{eff} = S \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \sin^2 \theta \quad (2)$$

The misorientation angle of CNTs in matrix to loading direction is θ . $\theta=0$, when CNTs are perfectly aligned through extrusion process. Thus, $S_{eff} = S$, where S is average aspect ratio ($= l/d$, length = 5 μm , diameter = 20 nm). In the calculation of yield strength, the yield strength value of the raw Al matrix is 53.0 MPa. By adding 0.38 vol% (0.2 wt%) CNTs, the calculated value is 78.2 MPa, well corroborated with the experimental yield strength of composite (84.8 MPa). We expect that the small variation may occur by other strengthening mechanisms such as the generation of dislocation by thermal mismatch and Orowan looping system. Therefore, it is fair to say that over 90% of the yield strength improvement is contributed from load transfer mechanism.

We can also predict the tensile strength by using the same model [13]. Tensile strength strongly depends on the length of reinforcement, which is not to be less than a critical length for the effective transfer in fiber shape reinforcement. The critical length is defined as follows in Eqn. (3).

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_{T,R} D}{2\tau_M} \quad (3)$$

where l_c is the critical length of the reinforcement (CNTs), $\sigma_{T,R}$ is the tensile strength of reinforcement which is 3.6 GPa for CNTs [17], D is the average diameter of reinforcement and τ_M is the matrix shear strength ($= \sigma_M/2$). The experimental tensile strength of matrix is 94.2 MPa (raw Al, Table 1). The calculated value of l_c is 0.78 μm , lower than length of CNTs (5 μm). In case of $l > l_c$, the following expression holds true (Eqn. 4) :

$$\sigma_{T,C} = \sigma_{T,R} V_R \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l} \right) + \sigma_{T,M} (1 - V_R) \quad (4)$$

The calculated value of tensile strength ($\sigma_{T,C}$) is 106.5 MPa, slightly lower than the experimental value for 0.2 wt% (115.9 MPa). We expect this difference to occur by the same reasons of the yield strength.

Sample		Raw Al	Al-0.2wt% CNT
<i>Yield strength</i>	[MPa]	53.0	84.8
<i>Tensile strength</i>	[MPa]	94.2	115.9
<i>Elongation</i>	[%]	17.0	9.5

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the raw Al and Al-CNT composites.

The differences of yield strength and tensile strength between calculated value and experiment value are only 7.8% and 8.1%, respectively. These results are obvious evidences that the dominant mechanism of strengthening is the load transfer. Thus, the shear lag model is effective for predicting the mechanical strength in Al-CNT composite.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we report that mechanical pulverization of Al with CNTs in paraffin oil prevented the oxidation of Al, that is critical for effective formation of covalent bonds between Al matrix and CNTs. Dispersion process of CNTs in DCE solution and the mixing process with pulverized Al were performed by sonication that minimized the damage of CNTs from mechanical impact. High temperature processes (sintering and melt blending) lead to covalent bonding (Al_4C_3) between Al and CNTs. The formed Al-C covalent bonds play a leading role in load transfer from Al matrix to CNTs. The yield strength and tensile strength of Al-CNT composite are improved by 60% and 23%, respectively, with an addition of 0.2 wt% CNTs. This enhancement is well corroborated with the predicted values from shear lag model that is based on the load transfer mechanism. Thus, the shear lag model is highly effective for predicting mechanical properties in Al-CNT composite.

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